

**Christian Missionaries Contribution towards Women Education: Special
Reference to Andhra Pradesh**

N.SIVASWETHA

Lecturer in History, PCR Junior College,
Chittor, Andhra Pradesh

ABSTRACT

French East India Companies encouraged the missionaries to spread Christianity however the changing atmosphere and their fortunes in India, especially after defeating the French troops affected the missions as well. The maximum stations in India now were within the areas conquered by the English. The first organised mission work for Muslim women and children, began in February 1884 in Chinna bazar in Guntur. The work among Muslim women was started by Mrs. Unangst, Dr. Kugleraiso gave medical treatment at their home. A school opened for Muslim girls in 1884 Mrs. Jane Rallier was the first single woman to learn Urdu. She worked among Muslim women upto 1903. Mrs. Jessie Thomas was assigned to work in 1908. Miss Thomas had six girls who knew Urdu and who worked with hears teachers and zenana workers.

Keywords: French, Women, Zenana Workers.

Introduction:

The context of European revivals forms the back drop within which Christian Missionaries came to India. The passing of the Charter Act 1613 by the British Parliament, colonial and political interests in and been encouraging the missionary movement

The spread of Christianity in India was due to the revival movement in Britain, The Societies prime motive was to save the unsaved people all over the world, it further imbued them with a civilizing mission. The policy of the colonial governments in India changing with the time for instance the Dutch. The latter immediately suspended the Jesuit missionary enterprise, with the end of French and Dutch power in India more or less the Roman Catholic power and activity was also on the decline and Protestantism was strengthened. An important aspect of Missionary work was Conversion and social service.

In Andhra, Conversions underwent a gradual phase of change, Individual and small group conversions of the early 19th century, were replaced at the end of the 19th century by mass conversion Movements. In the Telugu speaking region Christian missions used several Effective methods to reach Hindus for conversion. For instance Education, Health and Famine relief works were the most Important agencies for the mass movements,

Women Missionaries became the pioneers of women's education. In the initial days the missionaries concentrated their activities only on men by men later they realized women were a neglected lot and took up the women emancipation. Up to 1858, missionary work was primarily regarded as men's work. Between 1858 and 1908, the number of women engaged in the mission especially the wives of the missionaries increased. Special/missionary societies were organized for women. The Zenana Bible and medical mission group set up with the title. The India female normal school and institution society". A large proportion of missionary school had only one teacher. The Andhra United Lutheran mission employed 1,513 teachers for 1,041 schools (These figures do not include the 81 college. High school and Bible Training schools). The church mission society reported that by 1931 the Krishna and West Godavari districts recorded 780 village schools with 1076 teachers¹⁰. The one teacher schools were at Cumbum 5 to 10, at Guntur 11 to 15. Vidyanagar 6 to 12.

The Church of England Zenana missionary society was formed in 1880¹.

Zenana was defined by Drach and Kudler Zenana is used by the Hindus to designate the post part of the house, particularly among the wealthy classes which is assigned to the female members of the household wives, mothers and daughters of the Hindu families. It was a place no stranger or no man could enter². In 1863 Miss Anna S Kugler and Miss. Fannie Dryden came to assist Mrs. unangstP Lucy in zenana³. Mrs. Unangst and Mrs. Schnure opened the Hindu girls school in 1883 in Guntur and Mangalagiri. These women urged Christians to educate their daughters. They appealed to Hindu and Muslims as well. The missions started school infour villages in Guntur area 65 percent of Christian boy's andonly⁴ percent of the girls attended the local missions schools.

In the schools of Vidyanagar area, in Krishna District girls formed 39.9 percent of the enrollment in the 1st standards and only 10.9 percent in other standards. Speaking of Guntur schools statistics show that girls formed 39.9 percent in the 1st standard and 22 percent in the other standards by 1926. The percentage of girls is the schools was 14.8 percent in Vidyanager and in Guntur it was 13.9 percent⁷. In 1885 it was decided by the Lutheran mission conference to educate woman in the congregation. In 1926 over 300 organizations were working among the converts for women. More than 36,700 were baptized and 5,500 could read the Bible⁸. The church hissionary sociely gives the record about schools in Krishna and west Godievan districts for 1026 and 1931⁹.

Year	No. of Schools	No. of Teachers	Non-Christian	Christian
1926	635	1031	10464	10954
1931	770	1076	11708	10020

Source picket The Chrisben mass Movements in India, p.28

Mrs. william J. Coutter opened the first girls school at Rajahmundryin 1852 16 1882. Mrs Schmidt stared a school for girls¹¹. The first zenana work began at Narsapuram. A district munsiff permitted his wilfe and daughter with five other members to be taught by Mrs Schmidt and Mrs Artman Artman continued with her workin 1890. Miss Agnes schude and Miss katherine Sadler arrived in Rajahmundry in 1891 Mrs Schade started a Hindu girls schools.¹² She showed a great deal of interest in educational field so that there came to be so many schools run by Rajahmundry mission.

More woman missionaries arrived as the work expanded. New Hinou girls schools were established in different parts of Rajahmundry and its outskirts. Miss Charlotte Swenson who arrived in 1906 that 270 home were visited weekly and 1200 women and children were under instruction. At the close of this period, in addition to the central girls school in Rajahmundry conducted by Miss Schade, Boarding schools were established in Samalkoland Bhimavaram in 1918-1919¹³. In 1920 twenty two women came to Rajahmundry to serve in Zanana and medical work. 82 In the Hermannsburg Mission field, a girl's school was established in 1869, with a connected boarding school at Gudur. After, the school was transferred to Kodur, where Mrs. Woerriein, who had an excellent Knowledge of Telugu developed the school and widened its activity When Woerrien become mission director, he made Gudur his head quarters in 1892, and the girl's 'school was transferred once more to that centre¹⁴. At first, this school was mostly for orphans and unwanted girls. The child ding was trained in cleanliness, orderliness and industry. The profit from the sale of Lace which was sold in Germany and America helped to support the school. Many of these girls became wives of native Christian workers. Woerriein's daughter, Magdalene became the first Zenane worker on July 23, 1901 At the end of the first year. They were assisted by Rachel, the widow of a catechist, who had been teaching in the girl's boarding school.

Miss Adele Schickinz arrived in 1904 to take over the work from Mrs. Woerlein and her daughter, the work expanded. A native teacher was employed for the fancy lace work. A school was built and completed in 1906, and Miss Martha Woerlein came in the next year to take the charge of the lace school. This relieved Miss Schichinz for full Zenana work. A new zenana station 83 was opened in Tirupati in 1908. Miss Schiekeinzi moved there when she was replaced in gudur by Miss Marthadrews The first baptism in Tirupati through Zenana work was the wife of the police Inspector, on July 17. 1910, in the next year 24 were baptized at Gudur.

Miss Schickinz married a missionary Linder in 1921, but continued in the work as her husband was located at Tirupati. In the same year two ceaconesses came out India to enter the work. Elsie Kastens and Anna Marie Meyberg. The work expanded in the next few years to Puttur, where Manekes wife supervised the work of two Bild women and two women teachers, one at the middle school and one is the elementary school Venkatag in 1914. She visited Rat's wife and found her literato Mere Zanand women were ready com Stom Germany for zenana work when the war broke out.

A Widow's home has been opened by Mrs. Sorbe in Katahası in 1908, but this was close during the war Another interesting feature of the women's work was the first women's conference held In Gudur under Mrs Woerttienis direction, on March 3, 1900 Subjects for discussion were the place of women in the homes (Christian and Hindu), the visitation of sick, the teaching of the uneducated and the improvement of home living Local women 84 samaje (sociatles) were recommended with one of its activhes to be sewing so that clothing could be prepared for the poor children. Before the war, the zenans work in the Hermansburg masion focused on 80 homes which were being contacted weekly with activities centering around hand work, bible stories and hymn singing Some were instructed in reading, the workers also visited many Christian women in their homes regularly¹⁵.

The missionary attack on the Hindu customs and social evils had an indirect influence on Andhra Social reformers “Leaders such as Raghupathi Venkataratnam Naidu. Mutnuri Kristina Rao and Konda Venkatapaian Panthulu came from the missionary institutions and were profoundly influenced by the ethical ideas, manners and conduct of Christian Missions. The social reform activities in relation to women and untouchables owed much to the influence of missionary teaching and inspiration of missionary work”¹⁶. Thus women missionary zeal of educating women had inspired the indian social reformer later and many Indian women were educated breaking the social barmers An attempt has been madei the paper to throw lighton the role played by the women missionaries in educating women in the Andhra region.

REFERENCES

1. Pickett, J. Waskon, Christian Mass Movements in India, Lucknow, 1933. P.278
2. Neil Stephen. The Story of Christian Church in Inoa and Pakistan C.L.S. Madras, 1922, P.105
3. Drach and Rudler. The Telugu Mission of the Ge seral Council and Evanglicallutherm Church America, Philadalphia, 1914, P.270, and Dolber ML A History of Lutheranism in Andhra Desa, New York, 1959. P:315
4. Dolbeer A History of Luthiernism, Op. Cit, P.103
5. Picket... Op., Clit, P.287
6. Ibid., and Swavely, CH. One Hundred Years in Andhra Country (1842-1942) Madras, 1942 P262-266.
7. Dolbeer. A History of Luthermism, Op. cit., P
8. Picket, Op, Cit., P.288
9. Ibid., P.281
10. Ibid, P285
- 11 Dolbeer, M.L. Brief History of Andhra Evangelical Lutheran Church, Church Publication, Rajahmundry, 1950.P.320.
12. Wole, F.B. After Fifty years or Historical Sketch of the Guntur Mission of the Evengelicalluthern Church of the General symod in U.S.A., Philedelphia, L.P. Society, 1896 P.254, Dolbeer, AELC Brief History, P20-21, 43-44
13. Drach, Kingdom Path Finders. Philadelphia 1942, 89-103. Swarely, One Hundred Years, P269 Dolbeer A.ELC. Brief History, P33, 50-53 Drach Kudler Op. Cit. P88. 205, 304, 310
14. Devadas, 75 Samvatsaramlu Klupta Charitra (Telurul Madras, 1941, P.30-37, 39 52.54, in Dolbeer
15. Ibid., P30-37, 50-54
16. E.Bhathy, Religious Minorities and Secular State in JR. Chandra and MM Thomas (eds) Religious Freedom, Bangalore, 1942 and A.V Thomas, Christians in Secularindia, Rutherford, 1974. Cited in Lionel Caplan Class and Chistianity in South India, Modern Asian Studies, Britain, 1980, P.652